

PANDEMIC CHALLENGES AND POST-PANDEMIC APPROACHES IN ROMANIAN SMART COMMUNITIES

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper aims to investigate the COVID-19 effects on innovation in urban management and (e)Governance.

Methodology/approach - As an approach, the primary qualitative observation method was used, combined with the literature review.

Findings – Crisis boosts innovation and creativity. As Smart Cities are a developing process in Romania and eGovernance was mostly at its beginning, the COVID-19 crisis expedited processes and helped burn stages in relevant domains. Local communities found ways to cope with the new reality. The crisis passed, vectors of modernization and innovation face opposing forces of resistance to change that were silenced during the pandemic.

Research limitations/implications – n/a.

Practical implications – Good practice examples where innovation and creativity shaped communities and support sustainable development, inspiring future generations.

Originality/value – Following the good practice examples of C, BM and B communities in Romania.

Key words: resilient communities, smart cities, innovation.

Introduction

"The concept [smart city] is an organic connection between technological, human and institutional components" (Nam and Pardo 2011).

"Smart cities - are like organisms that develop an artificial nervous system, which allows them to behave in an intelligent and coordinated way. The new intelligence of cities is then found in the effective combination of digital telecommunications networks (nerves), ubiquitous intelligence (brains), sensors and hinges (sensory organs) and software solutions (knowledge and cognitive competence)" (Chourabi, et al. 2012).

"Smart city is a concept in which citizens, objects, utilities, etc., connect in an easy way using ubiquitous technologies, to significantly improve the quality of life in urban environments of the 21st century" (R. P.-S. Dameri 2014).

"Smart City refers to a city where ICT strengthens freedom of expression and accessibility of information and public services" (Anthopoulos 2011)

The article proposes to follow pandemic-post pandemic experiments in the cities of B, C and BM, in the context of digitalization, EU funding and social innovation, as cyber-physical boundaries disappear (Tushar and Faiz 2022).

Pandemic effects on Smart City initiatives in Romania

Cities across Europe, and especially Romania are heterogeneous entities. Development or lack of development is not ubiquitous. Diverse communities are created within cities, on criteria such as neighborhood, social status, age, occupation, hobbies, or even political principles. The diversity raises

challenges that cannot be tackled on a city scale, while solutions often work for certain groups only (Pop, Lobonțiu and Lobonțiu 2019).

Resilience against disasters in Romania is ensured at a national and local level by authorities such as the General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations, as well as municipalities and volunteer groups. (Pop, Lobonțiu and Lobonțiu 2019).

Romania's first smart cities initiatives began in 2005-2006, in Oradea, with integrated eGovernance systems, replicated in the coming years in Baia Mare or Ciugud. However, the advancement of Smart City technologies was limited, and even partly blocked during the 2008-2009 financial and economic crisis, only for the concept to be re-discovered in late 2016. Cities like Cluj-Napoca or Alba Iulia began a swift process of digital transformation, leveraging opportunities like EU funding for the first and the highly developed local ICT industry for the later. A hype started across Romania, having the National Electronic Payment System (ghiseul.ro) and the four very different good practice examples in Oradea, Cluj-Napoca, Alba Iulia and small village of Ciugud. As many municipalities started following the innovation leaders, the COVID-19 expedited steps towards digitalization, mostly towards Smart People (digital education and literacy) as well as Smart Governance (digital public services).

Most municipalities were forced to innovate, as to reduce direct human interaction, while having limited technical, financial, and legal support from the National Authorities. Some cities (successful ones) teamed-up with solution providers to deliver easy to use platforms for citizen interaction and digital public service, while others opted for "traditional" approaches such as email.

Service providers were, at turn, forced to adapt and innovate, as teams left offices for home in a new, uncharted territory of remote work. Workflows, timetables changed, and the integration of beginners seemed, at first, impossible. Employees lingered for interaction and online meetings seemed a poor replacement for the traditional standard.

Two years after the pandemic outburst, the „Uberization” of work transformed the workplace forever. Innovation teams tend to refuse returning to „the office”, often threatening to quit their jobs if a mandatory return was put in place.

These digital interaction habits created expectations not only towards the workplace, but also administrative authorities, where citizens expect and demand digital service. This has given a boost to digitalization but is forcing city innovators to find new methods for community binding in a digital, post-pandemic era.

A major bottleneck in fulfilling citizen expectations is bureaucracy, often enforced by legislation, as well as Romanian's authorities to create digital bureaucracy (or digitizing bureaucracy) rather than performing digital transformation processes. Although the Pandemic forced digitalization and Government ordinances made it mandatory for public authorities to accept electronic document transfers and online requests, most bureaucratic processes remained unchanged.

The government failed implementing (at least in part) the Once Only Principle in terms of data and documents owned or produced by public authorities. "The 'once-only' principle (OOP) is a crucial element in the delivery of the user-friendly digital public services and modernization of public administration. Providing the same data repeatedly is troublesome and time-consuming both for citizens and businesses. It is also not reasonable since most of the data is already stored in authoritative sources. The key is to enable public administration to retrieve it in an efficient and safe way" (Marmot et al, 2021).

The absence of constraints towards data owners, mainly central authorities as well as the inexistence of identity verification, certification and management systems forced local authorities to create their own identity management systems, as well as to digitalize bureaucracy. Consequently, all physical dossiers (including copies of ID documents, certificates or attestations) were moved to the digital space (often scanned and emailed).

A special approach targeted social aids management, where the legislation specifically describes the *physical dossiers, including signed, stamped and certified copies of documents*. Thereby, on one hand, legislation forces cities to own physical documents, on the other it forces them to accept online interactions, on the other hand, public servants are forced to verify and create physical dossiers.

Several cities were already implementing digitalization processes, often funded through Administrative Capacity Operational Program. Some managed to include new functionalities, and even innovate in some respects. Leveraging on the funding available and pandemic regulations, many Romanian cities digitized their interaction with citizens, including tax payment, tax declarations, urban planning certificates and even construction authorizations. Some cities even started to innovate in social aids management, where legislation regarding dossiers was most "digital-resistant". A first Step taken by the city of BM and A was to accept online documentations, verify them, request clarification or additional documents where needed and then, on an agreed schedule, invite citizens to deliver the physical dossiers. Several advantages were quickly identified for this method. First, the amount of time people has spent in queues decreased, and the return rate for missing or unacceptable documents was significantly reduced. Second, the public servants were able to better manage their work-time. Third, and most important, this process opened the path towards online / printed dossiers out of the online system as well as digitally archived dossiers.

The digital transformation of public services created another need – that of validation of online documents and fraud prevention. At a local level, this facilitated (or forced) systems' integration. Although theoretically presented and "desired" in the past years, the implementation of the "once only principle" was never a priority, as technical (or financial costs regarding technical aspects), logistic and regulatory barriers were showstoppers.

At a local level, authorities began to understand that systems' integration is a sine qua non prerequisite for delivering secure, decent and ubiquitous online public services. Cross-department validations are feasible in all 3 cities of the study, as integration services are available providing information about social aids, property, tax payment or the agricultural register.

The city of BM and C have requested integration with national systems, including identity management, but central authorities refused interoperability.

However, good practice examples at a local level managed to inspire central authorities and a process of creating specific legislation was put in place, forcing central authorities too cooperate and create digital services that any public authority can use depending on its specific needs and activity.

A special case of innovation was the city of C, whose mayor has made it his mission to have Romania's first paperless and cashless city hall. Though his efforts have started in the early 2000, the pandemic gave him further silver bullets against the bureaucracy monster. Though the city provided several online tax payment methods (bank transfers, local card payment solution and integration in Romania's National Electronic Payment System – www.ghiseul.ro), the elderly preferred cash payments, creating queues at the cashier's office. Forced by the pandemic to reduce human interaction, the city decided to use a machine for cash tax payment. Due to supply chain issues and high demand for that type of machinery, the only available option was one that could not provide change, thereby people being forced to have the exact amount. This was highly frustrating for the local community, as, in theory, they had to visit the city hall twice: once to find out their due tax amounts and a second to bring exact change. The machine implementation was doubled by a dismissal of cashier payments. The city's solution to the issue was having the cashier exchange money, but not accept payments, if a machine was unable to provide change. As soon as a machine providing change was available, it replaced the old one. But innovation did not stop there. The city consists of several villages, and mobility for tax payment needed to be reduced. A cooperation agreement was created with local shops in each village and similar machinery for tax payment were placed in the local stores, so people could use them when shopping. Furthermore, if people were going to pay their taxes, they also made purchases from the local stores, thereby leading to a win-win situation.

Further innovation in the city of B – after implementing an online portal and mobile app for eGovernment, that included local issues reporting tools, the city was disappointed by a relatively small, recurring and counter-productive citizen-interaction regarding city problems. Thereby, it acknowledged that a city-reporting tool tends to reduce morale, both for citizens, the administration and, in the end, a worsened cooperation between the two. This was caused by an unrealistic citizens expectation that a pothole or broken bench should and could be fixed as soon as it is reported. The city needed to create a positive context for its reporting app. An innovative idea came to place, respectively a contest for the city's most beautiful garden and balcony. The app was enriched by a voting functionality, and mixed positive content with city problems, sweetening the entire context.

A third example is the city of BM, which, from its desire to improve its image and citizen participation, decided to implement participatory budgeting. Characterized by a huge lack of trust between citizens and the local administration, the city failed the process, with a small number of participants and an even smaller number of valuable projects. However, the city understood the need for digitalization, sustainability and a better understanding of the community's needs and expectations. It decided to create a Smart City Strategy. Involving some of the country's best consultants on smart cities, it created a participatory framework designed to identify local innovators, innovation projects and local companies that could support and co-create the BM Smart City. Using on-line campaigns, the consultants attempted to reach a wide group of stakeholders. The public consultation process was supposed to be different from anything that was ever done in a strategic context in the country, respectively leverage on technology and digital asynchronous interaction, rather than private stakeholder meetings. Social Media leading to questionnaires were presented on over 60.000 screens and impacted (was read by) at least 23.000 people, and over 5000 post interactions were registered. Despite the impressive numbers (for a 120.000 inhabitants city), under 100 (mostly negative or unrelated) comments were registered and less than 10 questionnaires were filled (despite their simplicity, ergonomics and small number of questions). Confronted with the refugee wave caused by the Ukrainian war, the same local community organized on Facebook groups to provide shelter, food and support for the refugees, becoming an international good practice example.

Thus counter-intuitive, smaller communities have better Smart City and eGovernance tools adoption rates.

Conclusions

The pandemic changed forever the way in which people expect to interact with authorities. Despite the creation of tools for eGovernance, two major (and opposing) trends were identified. Communities already used to participatory processes and co-creation have become even more inclusive and collaborative, breaking boundaries and speeding up the digital transformation process, while digital resistant communities have, at most, digitalized bureaucracy.

Often using the same technical tools (so not needing to consider and analyze users' digital literacy, ergonomics of the software or other technical aspects), similar communities found themselves obtaining different results in terms of adoption.

Although digitalization appears as an impersonal process, digital transformation tends to create its own bottlenecks and boundaries, often similar or derived from the physical interaction processes, such as mistrust, lack of involvement, bureaucracy, poor legal frameworks or a general negative attitude towards change.

Communities striving at becoming smarter (in the context of smart cities), resilient (in face of crisis, pandemics, natural disasters or war) or more sustainable (in terms of climate-change resilience and mitigation, sustainable resource usage, etc.) need to build trust between local stakeholders. As shown by the Cluj Innovation Camps taking place in the past 5 years (European Commission, 2017), (Transilvania IT, 2020), in order to achieve the Smart City Status, a city needs to take a step back and become a facilitator, rather than a driver. It needs to team up with local organizations, innovators and create a framework for them to educate, evolve and create an ecosystem of cross-domain, politics free digital transformers.

The pandemic and post-pandemic context have transformed citizen expectations in terms of public service delivery. However, the (apparently) inherent reverse effect of increasing participation and citizen involvement through digital channels did not happen in communities where co-creation was not already in place before the pandemic.

Although Romania's Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) is Europe's lowest, this is not mostly due to a lack of digital services or digital literacy, but rather a result of the citizens' lack of involvement, participation, trust, and desire for a true digital transformation (possibly even fear or resistance to change).

Smart Communities development needs to base itself on the relevant pillars of Smart Cities, and support the parallel development of Smart Economies, Smart People, Smart Environment, Smart Mobility, Smart

Living and Smart Governance, as the extensive development of one component ignoring the others causes more discrepancies and smaller adoption rates, generating negative contexts.

Further research needed

Digital transformation processes towards smart city implementations and the progress of Romania's existing Smart(er) City initiatives should be studied from a citizen's participatory point of view.

The existing Smart City tools implemented by municipalities need to be revised and their impact on the local quality of life needs to be assessed thoroughly.

It is also important to assess why existing tools provide different results in different communities, and an extensive assessment of uptake barriers is recommended.

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